

ETIOPATHOGENIC AND ANATOMO-CLINICAL ASPECTS IN POSTOPERATIVE EVISCERATIONS

Dragos F. Voicu

MD, PhD.,

Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital

Associated Profesor

“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania

Adrian Drăgan MD

MD, Braila County Emergency Hospital

Abstract

Postoperative eviscerations involve protrusion of intra-abdominal organs through a destroyed surgical wound. They represent a rare but constant surgical complication in surgery and are associated with significant morbidity and mortality, even if managed promptly.

The paper aims to review, based on personal experience and statistics, the etiopathogenic and anatomoclinical aspects of eviscerations, as well as preventive and curative measures.

Increased awareness among surgeons and clinicians is crucial, especially given the reports of late and atypical presentations.

Keywords: postoperative evisceration, surgical emergencies

INTRODUCTION

Complete postoperative eviscerations (total eviscerations) are defined as protrusions of the abdominal viscera, a consequence of dehiscence of all abdominal planes sutured after laparotomy. This complication is a constant presence in emergency surgery services, with a significant increase in the duration of hospitalization, as well as its costs.

Despite the advances made in surgery in recent decades, progress materialized in the use of biologically inert sutures, effective antibiotic therapy and efficient hemostasis methods, eviscerations still represent a problem today associated with an incidence of 0.25 – 1.5%, and with a mortality between 9 and 44%.

Evisceration is considered to be the result of a complex of factors, both local and systemic, the most common being age over 65 years, male gender, intra-abdominal or wound infections, emergency surgery, abdominal compartment syndrome, neoplasms, digestive fistulas, intestinal occlusions, hypoproteinemia or the presence of ascites. In addition, diabetes mellitus, anemic syndromes, alcoholism, cardiac or pulmonary diseases are also considered to be risk factors for the occurrence of evisceration.

Various associations of the mentioned factors include the patient in the high-risk group with regard to this complication. Evisceration is a common reason for immediate reintervention, their severity making it necessary to have a correct preoperative evaluation of the patient with regard to this risk.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

During the period January 2015 - December 2025, in the 1st Surgery Clinic of the Brăila of the County Emergency Hospital, 16 cases of complete evisceration were recorded, out of a total of 8780 abdominal interventions (0.18%) performed.

Only cases of complete evisceration were taken into account, incomplete (blocked) eviscerations being excluded. The cases were retrospectively analyzed from the point of view of risk factors, but also from the

point of view of resolution methods, subsequent morbidity and mortality.

Thus, 9 cases were male, and in 7 cases evisceration occurred in women. The average age was 68 years, with a range between 42 and 85 years.

The initial pathology, with surgical indication, included the following types of conditions:

- colon neoplasm: 5 cases;
- acute calculous pycholecystitis: 2 cases;
- abscessed appendiceal plastron: 2 cases;
- abdominal trauma: 2 cases;
- perforated gastric ulcer: 2 cases;
- recurrent multiple incarcerated eventrations: 2 cases;
- intestinal obstruction by strangulated inguinal-scrotal hernia: 1 case.

Regarding the risk factors cited in the literature, the following data were found in our study:

- emergency surgery: 12 cases;
- wound infections: 11 cases;
- age over 65 years: 8 cases;
- hypoalbuminemia (< 6g %): 7 cases;
- anemia: 6 cases;
- obesity: 10 cases;
- neoplasia: 5 cases;
- chronic alcoholism: 3 cases;
- diabetes mellitus: 3 cases;
- digestive fistulas: 2 cases;
- jaundice: 1 case;
- steroid use: 1 case.

From the analysis of the presented data, it emerged that in our statistics emergency surgery (75%) and wound infections (68.8%) were mainly involved as risk factors, the latter being usually justified as a result of severe intra-abdominal infections. Although we did not objectively record an abdominal hypertension syndrome in any patient, alterations in mental status were also present in 1 case (delirium tremens and postoperative psychosis), with marked agitation and with a diffi-

cult response to specific medication, the episodes of agitation being obviously associated with an increase in intra-abdominal pressure.

Regarding the association of risk factors, in our study the association of several risk factors was found:

- 3 risk factors: 2 cases;
- 4 risk factors: 4 cases;
- 5 risk factors: 6 cases;
- 6 risk factors: 1 case;
- 7 risk factors: 1 case.

Regarding the surgical treatment applied, in the analyzed cases:

- in 8 cases, total threads on rubber rings were used, with the inclusion of all layers of the abdominal wall in the suture;
- in 7 cases the parietal aponeurosis was sutured and associated total threads on rubber rings; in 2 of these cases the material used was represented by metal threads;
- one single case was resolved by using a substitution mesh, to avoid abdominal compartment syndrome.

Each time, the reintervention was performed in immediate emergency and aimed at the least traumatic reinsertion of the viscera, into the peritoneal cavity, its toilet with physiological betadine serum, the minimally traumatic dissection of the postoperative formed adhesions and the placement of the omentum as widely as possible, so that it would be interposed between the abdominal viscera and the parietal suture.

At the parietal level, the intervention aimed each time the most complete excision of the gangrenous infected aponeurotic tissues, the suture being performed in full healthy tissue and avoiding the formation of that "string" of thread at the intraperitoneal level, a consequence of an incorrect loading of the abdominal parietal layers in the suture.

Postoperative complications were relatively frequent (51%):

- wound suppuration: 3 cases;
- bronchopneumonia: 2 cases;
- upper digestive bleeding: 1 case;
- evisceration (recurrence): 1 case;
- recurrence of an intestinal fistula: 1 case.

There were not recorded other complications such as mechanical-inflammatory occlusion or abdominal compartment syndrome. The free interval between the initial intervention and the moment of evisceration was on average 9 days, with values ranging 3-20 days from the initial operative moment. The average number of days of hospitalization was 21 days, with range 15-32 days.

The mortality was 2 cases, respectively 12.5%, in accordance with data from the literature.

DISCUSSION

Postoperative eviscerations represented a relatively rare complication in our statistics, being encountered with a frequency of 0.18% compared to the number of surgical interventions.

The recorded data revealed that it appeared as a major surgical complication, which required immediate

reintervention in all situations, being usually the prerogative of patients over 65 years of age, in emergency surgery conditions and with a large surgical procedure.

Male patients were more numerous, but in a smaller proportion than those present in the literature. Thus, gender cannot be considered a strong, important, risk factor in the evaluation of each patient.

Wound infections appeared in our work as the most significant risk factor, along with emergency surgery. The occurrence of wound infection was most often justified by severe intra-abdominal infections, but in addition, hemostasis defects, intraoperative contamination, or superinfection of seromas can be incriminated. Microbial cultures from the wound usually revealed *S. Aureus* or *E. Colli*; sometimes, polymicrobial cultures were also detected.

Regarding the association of comorbidities, evident in the analyzed case series (3-5 associated predisposing factors), this can be considered an important risk in assessing the potential for postoperative evisceration.

In our study, the type of incision did not appear to be a relevant risk factor, although in the vast majority of cases it was a median incision. Although they do not appear as risk factors in the literature, in our study there was 1 case, in which patients developed post-operatively, prior to evisceration, alterations in mental status, with marked agitation, a possible risk factor due to increased intra-abdominal pressure. This complication also appears in other studies, as extremely rare (van Gelden, Poole).

Post-evisceration complications occurred with an incidence of 51%, while the mortality was 12.5%, aspects that fully justify the importance of this complication. Experience has shown that epiploic interposition at the parietal musculoaponeurotic suture level can be a technical solution for protecting the viscera, especially in the setting of a severe infectious complication of the surgical wound. However, omentum mobility and intestinal peristalsis do not always achieve this technical objective.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Total postoperative eviscerations represent serious surgical complications, which usually require immediate emergency reintervention.

2. The patient with evisceration thus appears as a patient in a serious condition, taking into account the surgical complication presented, the possibility of co-existence of other surgical complications (digestive fistula, mechanical-inflammatory occlusion, septic state, etc.), the postoperative evolution being burdened by the frequent occurrence of new post-intervention complications.

3. The high mortality and morbidity that the patient with evisceration presents, as well as the significant increase in costs and days of hospitalization, make this problem require appropriate attention, with risk analysis of each case. So the use of total anti-evisceration sutures, careful hemostasis, abundant lavage of the peritoneal cavity and of the surgical wound are routine measures in every surgical case, especially in patients with a high risk of postoperative evisceration.

References

1. Omejc A, Janša V, Kobal B, Barbič M. Spontaneous transvaginal intestinal evisceration two years after vaginal hysterectomy: A case report. *Medicina*. 2024;60(9):1388.
2. Varlas VN, Bălescu I, Varlas RG, Adnan A-A, Filipescu AG, Bacalbaşa N, Suciu N. Complete abdominal evisceration after open hysterectomy: A case report and evidence-based review. *J Clin Med*. 2025;14(1):262
3. Ballová Z, Vasilenko T, Gašparová P, Dosedla E. Bowel evisceration one year after total laparoscopic hysterectomy: A case report. *Actual Gynecol Obstet*. 2025;17:1-4.
4. Ordonez Juarez J, Villanueva Herrero J, Jimenez Bobadilla B, Oropeza R, Alvarado Tamez E, Solis Hidalgo P. Transvaginal evisceration of the small bowel: A rare postoperative complication after hysterectomy.
5. Salvetti F. Sneeze-induced transvaginal small bowel evisceration and obstruction nine months after iatrogenic vaginal vault laceration: A case report. *Case Rep Emerg Surg Trauma*. 2024;2(1):26
6. Horton CE. Recurrent vaginal evisceration of abdominal contents with subsequent resection of necrotic omentum in a 35-year-old woman. *J Surg Case Rep*. 2024;2024(3):127
7. Rodriguez-Hermosa, J.I., Codina-Cazador, A., Ruiz-Feliu, B., et al. Risk factors for acute abdominal dehiscence after laparotomy in adults. *Cir. Esp.*, 2005, 77:280
8. Khan, M.N., Naqvi, A.H., Irshal, K., et al. - Frequency and risk factors of abdominal wound dehiscence. *J. Coll. Physicians Surg. Pak*, 2004, 14:355
9. Rodriguez – Hermosa, J.I., Ruiz–Feliu, B., Roig – Garcia, J., et al. Hepatic evisceration after cholecystectomy in a superobese patient. *Obesity Surgery*, 2008, 18:1653
10. Mazilu O., Cnejevici S., Prundeanu H. et al. Evisceratiile postoperatorii: factori de risc si corelatii clinice, *Revista Chirurgia (Buc.)*, 2009, 104(4)
11. Voicu, D.F., Firescu, D, Serban, Cristina, et al. Open abdomen procedure in the management of severe intraabdominal sepsis, *Analele Universității “Dunărea de Jos” Galați Medicină Fascicula XVII*, 2014,2: 111-114